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Master Thesis

Construction and Application of Topic Curriculum Graphs

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Abstract

This research aims to propose an improved approach to provide a broader and well-structured understanding of curriculum content, by connecting the gaps presented by traditional learning methods. The main focus of this study lies on developing a well-structured, comprehensive Topic Curriculum Graph (TCG), which is envisioned to act as a visual platform for analysis, facilitating both educators and students to navigate the curriculum landscape more effectively. The TCG offers a new lens for understanding how the representation of course content and student learning trajectories.

The research goes in-depth into the concept of Graphs, exploring components like ontologies, schemas, and the Resource Description Framework (RDF). In particular, it analyzes the role and significance of TCGs in providing a comprehensive and structured understanding of curriculum content. The study also delves into the understanding of Learning outcomes and Course Objectives, providing frameworks and methodologies for their evaluation. This is done by exploring the different approaches to learning and how they can be used to represent the sequence of skills and knowledge that students need to acquire. The research proposes an ontology-based model that can be used to define course objectives and ensure their alignment with the TCG.

Furthermore, the study highlights a blueprint for executing this research, illustrating the input data sources, techniques for assessment, and process of creating the CKG, followed by their actual implementation. The implementation of the CKG is done using an RDF-based approach, which allows the CKG to be queried and visualized using existing tools and frameworks. The research also discusses the use of the CKG as a tool for analyzing student performance and identifying areas where further support may be needed.

Overall, this research explores a more meaningful paradigm for understanding, representing, and analyzing academic curricula. The use of a TCG provides a comprehensive and structured approach to curriculum design and analysis,

which can help educators and students to understand the inner structure of a curriculum and navigate it more effectively. By providing a more comprehensive and structured understanding of curriculum content, this research can help to bridge the gaps presented by traditional learning methods, leading to more effective learning outcomes.

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1

Introduction

Traditional university course cataloguing processes have served as reference points for both educators and students. These descriptions, while comprehensive, are primarily subjective, and crafted by educators based on their perspective of the course. With the growing emphasis on data-driven decisions in educational institutions, relying solely on these descriptions might not provide a complete representation of a course's nuances, potentially impacting curriculum design, student choices, and learning outcomes(3). This study delves into an innovative method to enhance the students' and educators' understanding of the academic landscape. Traditional methods often leave gaps in expressing the complexity of a curriculum. By developing a structured and objective representation of academic content, we aim to bridge these gaps and provide a clearer view of course content. Our primary approach lies in constructing a Topic Curriculum Graph (TCG) that accurately encapsulates the intricate structure of a curriculum. Fundamentally a visual analysis platform, the TCG seeks to aid educators and students in navigating the curriculum landscape with increased proficiency. The study attempts to redefine curricular understanding and explores how TCK influences the representation of course content, and student outcomes. The study aims to analyse knowledge graphs techniques and features to construct a graph representation of curricula. We start with defining TCG as,

A Topic Curriculum Graph (TCG) is an interconnected graph of topics used to represent

TCG is not a Knowledge Graph but utilises some aspects of KGs such as schemas, ontologies and relations. But to understand a TCG, we must also understand the concepts of a Knowledge Graphs and their usage in the field of educational resource management.

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1.1 Motivation

The challenges posed by the limitations of conventional cataloging methods underscore the necessity for a more systematic, data-driven approach.(4) There's a growing consensus in the academic community about the potential advantages of integrating modern data representation methods, such as Knowledge Graphs, into curriculum planning and analysis. By providing an objective, structured representation of course content, we aim to bridge the gaps left by traditional methods, offering students and educators a clearer view of the academic landscape. Constructing a TCG using Knowledge Graph techniques allows us an insight to the networked structure and operations compared to a traditional tabular data structure.

By integrating additional data, such as student enrollment and learning outcomes, KGs benefit teachers by simplifying course comparison and providing insights into areas for improvement in course design and delivery. Understanding the relationships between concepts, courses, and learning outcomes allows teachers to tailor their curricula better to address students' needs and interests, ultimately enhancing the learning experience and improving student engagement, motivation, and satisfaction.

KGs also contribute to more efficient resource allocation within academic institutions. By analyzing data on resource allocation, institutions can prioritize using resources, such as classrooms, faculty, and equipment, reducing costs and increasing efficiency.

1.1.1 Benefiting Stakeholders

- **Teachers:** Simplify course comparison, gain insights into areas for improvement in course design and delivery, and tailor curricula to address students' needs and interests.
- **Students:** Experience more engaging, motivating, and satisfying learning experiences through customized curricula that better align with their needs and interests.
- **Academic Institutions:** Make informed decisions about course design, student engagement, and resource allocation, ultimately reducing costs and increasing efficiency.
- **Researchers:** Contribute to understanding knowledge graph effectiveness and best practices, driving innovation and improvements in the education sector.

1.2 Research Question

In this research, we explore the techniques to construct a comprehensive and well-organized educational graph that accurately represents the internal structure of a curriculum. The resulting Topic Curriculum Graph (CKG) is intended to serve as a visual analysis platform, aiding educators and students in navigating and understanding the curriculum landscape more effectively and addressing how TCGs influence the representation and understanding of course content.

How do Topic Curriculum Graphs aid in understanding and representation of course content?

Since the research question is quite complex, let's divide it into a few sub research questions.

- **SRQ1:** Which Schema is preferred for a TCG?
- **SRQ2:** How can we construct a TCG from Current Curricula?
- **SRQ3:** Which tools and techniques are necessary to construct a TCG?
- **SRQ4:** How can a TCG be utilised to represent a course?

1.3 Document Outline

The document begins with the Introduction, where the core purpose and context of the research are provided. Following this, the Background chapter offers an in-depth exploration of the academic course cataloging realm. This chapter gives attention to the concept of the Knowledge Graph, elucidating its vital components, ontologies, and schemas. Further, the Resource Description Framework (RDF) and its primary components are explored. This chapter concludes with an insight into Course Objectives, presenting their foundational principles.

The subsequent Design chapter provides a blueprint for the research. This chapter elucidates the sources of input data for the study, delves into the intricate process of constructing the Topic Course Graph (TCG), and describes techniques employed for evaluating course objectives.

In the Implementation chapter, readers are guided through the practical application steps of the study. It systematically outlines the procedures from the initial stages of TCG construction to the assessment of course objectives, emphasizing the methodologies and tools used.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Results chapter presents the findings of the research. Key issues are discussed, such as challenges faced during automatic graph generation. This chapter also sheds light on the methods and results of evaluating course objectives.

Following the results is the validation of the results where we analyze the results of this findings before accepting or rejecting the results. This chapter also sheds light on the shortcomings of the study.

A thorough Discussion follows, where the research outcomes are analyzed, debated, and contextualized, giving readers a comprehensive understanding of the significance and implications of the findings.

Then, the Conclusion chapter encapsulates the essence of the research, summarizing the main discoveries and their broader impact on the academic community. The manuscript concludes with a References section, presenting a list of academic sources consulted during the research process.

The document wraps up with The Future Work segment highlights potential directions for subsequent research and improvements. This includes suggestions like refining semantic structures, integrating feedback mechanisms, expanding data sources, and scaling the methodologies.

2

Background

In order to construct a Topic Curriculum Graph (TCG), we must first understand Knowledge Graphs and how Knowledge Graphs are currently being utilised in academic management. We study KGs as we derive a definition of TCG from them.

2.1 Knowledge Graph

A Knowledge Graph(KG) is a structured representation of information where entities (nodes) connect through relationships (edges). This graph-based approach allows for the modeling of complex systems and relationships intuitively and computationally efficiently. Knowledge graphs originated from the semantic web and artificial intelligence world and can effectively represent complex interrelations, allowing an intuitive understanding of information structures(5).

Understanding relationships between topics, concepts, and broader subjects becomes crucial within the educational framework. KGs provide a visual, interconnected map of these relationships, allowing for insightful analysis and potential personalization based on the data's structure.

2.1.1 Key Components

- **Entities (Nodes):** These are individual items or concepts in a KG, often representing real-world objects or abstract concepts. Examples include "Course," "Domain," or "Topic."

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- **Relationships (Edges):** These define the connections between entities and describe how one entity relates to another. For example, a "teaches" relationship might connect a "Teacher" entity to a "Course" entity.

Figure 2.1: Example Knowledge Graph (1)

2.1.2 Ontologies

Ontologies intersect philosophy and computer science as formalized knowledge representations within specific domains. These representations encode concepts or classes and their relationships, establishing a structured framework for interpreting and organizing information. Beyond simple hierarchical categorization, ontologies capture richer, multi-dimensional relationships, supporting reasoning and inference. Ontologies focus on the abstract representation of domain-specific knowledge, enabling sense and semantic understanding. (5)

2.2 Resource Description Framework (RDF)

2.1.3 Schemas

Schemas are a concrete instantiation of this knowledge in the data layer of a KG. They define specific types of entities, their properties, and their possible relationships. Schemas are the blueprint for data entry, validation, and querying, ensuring data coherence and consistency. Schemas emphasize the concrete instantiation of this knowledge, guaranteeing logical coherence and data consistency in KG implementations(5).

2.2 Resource Description Framework (RDF)

RDF is a standard model, developed by the W3C, for describing resources on the web. At its heart, RDF is about making statements about resources in the form of subject-predicate-object expressions, often termed as "triples".

Figure 2.2: RDF Terminology (2)

Figure 2.3: RDF Graph of Beatles (2)

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2.2.1 Cardinal Components

- **Subject:** The primary resource under delineation.
- **Predicate:** The relational descriptor elucidating the nexus between the subject and an object.
- **Object:** Epitomizing the target or resultant of the declared relationship.

2.3 Learning Trajectories

Learning trajectories describe the progressive pathways students commonly traverse as they advance in understanding and skills within specific academic domains. Each trajectory comprises a sequence of instructional tasks to facilitate students' progression from a starting point to a learning goal(6).

The analysis of learning trajectories seeks to understand the nuances of student progression through a particular domain, identify common challenges or misconceptions, and optimize instructional interventions to cater to diverse learning needs.

2.4 Course Objective

The Course Objectives encompass a comprehensive summary of the course contents and are typically outlined in the course catalogue for each class. These objectives serve as a valuable reference point for both students and instructors, outlining the desired learning outcomes and goals of the course. Additionally, they provide a framework that facilitates instructional material design, assessment method selection, and evaluation of student performance. (7)

2.5 Related Work

The study of curriculum understanding and optimization using knowledge graphs has gained significant attention in recent years. It is crucial to thoroughly review relevant literature to comprehend the current approaches and identify areas that require further investigation.

2.5.1 Scope

This review was focused on three specific categories to narrow down the scope of research. The first category examined the construction of curriculum-based knowledge graphs, while the second analyzed learning trajectories using these graphs. Finally, the third category investigated course objectives. By segmenting the broad research question in this way, we provided a targeted and relevant review encompassing a wide range of related works.

2.5.2 Methodology

The works reviewed in this section were sourced from academic journals and Google Scholar, ensuring scholarly rigor and relevance. Most of these papers have been published in reputable journals, further enhancing the credibility of the reviewed content.

We only opt for papers that utilize an academic or curriculum knowledge graph and thus the related work is quite limited.

2.5.3 Construction of Knowledge Graph

Stahr et al., present a methodology for constructing a knowledge graph based on the curriculum system. The goal of this approach is to address issues related to the lack of intuitive display and clarity in the curriculum system, as well as time-consuming manual error inspection. By organizing curriculum context and error information more effectively, students and teachers will benefit from improved understanding and management of the curriculum. Additionally, this study analyzes the relationship between various parts of courses offered by the CSE department at Miami University with a focus on preceding and subsequent components(8).

Yu Et al., present a construction scheme for a curriculum system that utilizes a knowledge graph. This approach effectively illustrates the logical connections between courses, thereby facilitating users' comprehension of course inter-dependencies without requiring them to sift through vast amounts of data. Additionally, the implementation of a knowledge graph can aid in identifying potential errors within the curriculum system and contribute to their rectification, consequently enhancing search efficiency and instructional convenience in modern contexts (9).

Chen et al., constructed a knowledge graph for a specific subject and validate its effectiveness through empirical experiments. The proposed system and constructed knowledge graphs are intended for integration into intelligent tutoring systems and Massive Open Online Course platforms, in order to facilitate personalized teaching services and adaptive

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Authors	Constructed KG	Addressed Curriculum Clarity	Logical Course Connections	Enhanced Search Efficiency	Integrated into Tutoring	User-Friendly Resources
Stahr et al.	✓	✓	✓			
Yu et al.	✓		✓	✓		
Chen et al.	✓				✓	
Dang et al.	✓			✓	✓	✓
Zhao et al.	✓					✓

Table 2.1: Comparison of Studies on Knowledge Graphs in Education

learning solutions. The paper is organized as follows: it begins by discussing related work, followed by an overview of the proposed system architecture, details on concept extraction and relation identification processes, and concludes with an exemplary case showcasing the evaluation results. However, further information is required to provide detailed outcomes such as the performance of the proposed system or specific results from the exemplary case study(10).

Dang et al., created a knowledge graph for Massive Open Online Courses. The graph contains 28,591 instances and their corresponding relations. This knowledge graph offers a user-friendly portal that assists learners in systematically and efficiently viewing and selecting learning behaviours. Moreover, users can readily access numerous resources from various platforms without encountering duplicate information. The graph has significantly contributed to organizing educational resources and enhancing the accessibility and efficiency of learning for users(11).

Zhao et al., constructed an educational knowledge graph that contains knowledge derived from textbooks. The primary goal of this paper is to present the EDUKG, an educational knowledge graph designed for K-12 education. The objective is to offer a user-friendly and practical resource that extracts detailed information from textbooks, enabling the exploration of innovative educational technologies and the development of educational applications. The results of this study involve the successful establishment and dissemination of the EDUKG, including its code, data, and application availability under the Creative Commons License. Furthermore, an open platform has been created to allow users access to extensive educational data and resources(12).

Authors	Semantic Solidity	Scalability	Re-usability	Execution Time
Stahr et al.			✓	High
Yu et al.				Medium-High
Chen et al.				Medium-High
Dang et al.	partially			High
Zhao et al.	✓	partially		High

Table 2.2: Limitations in Existing Study of Education KGs

2.5.4 Course Objective

Aliya et al., developed a knowledge graph for managing university courses. The knowledge graph facilitates meaningful linking of entities and their relations, offering valuable applications in domains such as Education, Biomedical, Electric Power Systems, the Automobile industry, Traditional Chinese Medicine, etc., enabling intelligent knowledge services. For detailed information on this paper’s objective and main contributions, please refer to its complete text. An accurate and comprehensive conclusion is essential in academia to address these aspects effectively(13).

2.5.5 Shortcomings of Existing Literature

Although the existing work does provide a KG for assessing courses and, thus, as a projection, the curriculum, they do not hold a priority for the semantics of the graph. The graph semantics only depend on the input data; the relation extractions are purely unsupervised. One exception is EduKG (12), but its construction goal is to understand the course rather than just course management. This allows EduKG to have complex relation between nodes but does not allow for an accurate representation of the course contents, mainly as it prioritizes interdisciplinary relations such as "influences" that is connected outside the scope. Though semantically solid, it is broad.

Another concern is scalability. As the graphs are constructed to show the structure of each course, they do not reuse the definitions made from previous courses. Each course content is stored exclusively for the course. This allows for faster graph connections and relations but also leads to a very high storage usage. A comparison of the lack of related work can be seen in Table 2.2

The graphs by Aliya (13) depicts a moderately accurate overview of the course but, sadly, is not semantically solid nor reusable and scalable. The overview also includes additional reading material in the course overview and thus falsifies the course description.

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This method of not limiting the course description to only the lectures and assignments and adding reading material such as textbooks and articles leads to a description and application of the reading materials over the course description.

The current work on Academic Graphs is novel and require further analysis. In this study we will aim to design a system to aid in addressing a few gaps in the study.

3

Design

The topic curriculum graph will serve as a framework for covering course topics and provide accurate course representation based on the course content. The first phase of this research will focus on analyzing an undergraduate and a graduate level computer science course, which will lay the foundation for potential future expansion(14).

Designing courses that consider adult learning principles has been introduced previously, yet effectively delivering such courses is still in its infancy. This research aims to streamline university resources and enhance topic coverage in course curricula. The graph will act as a blueprint for course topic coverage.

3.1 Design Goal

We aim to build a web portal with an interactive graph containing a network of topics. The primary goal is to represent courses as a network of topics following a visible hierarchy. Having such a system in the field of education is important and in this study we will try a case study of representing two courses as a network of topics. For this study, we will create specific ontologies and schemas usable by TCG to cater to the course and curricula represented in Datanose. The system should allow for topic addition, deletion and updating on the portal through seem-less server querying.

3.2 Input Source

The input source selection plays a crucial role in determining the quality of the graph. In this case, we have meticulously chosen two university courses as our sources, incorporating indexed list of topics from these courses. Our decision to include both undergraduate and

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Figure 3.1: Design to Construct TCG

graduate-level courses is driven by the accessibility of their lecture materials, which aids us in constructing a comprehensive TCG.

- Undergraduate Level - Course: Distributed and Parallel Programming - 5062COPP6Y
- Graduate Level - Course: Web Data Processing Systems - XM_40020

We highlight yet again that these courses were selected only due to the availability of course content and do not have any other significance for their selection.

To extract viable information and description of these courses to use as an input source, we can either analyze their lecture slides or a manually constructed list of topics for each course. Lecture slides often present condensed, key points on a given topic, while a structured list of topics offers a hierarchical understanding of the content covered. Below we will analyze which is more suitable and realistic input source.

3.2.1 Lecture Slides

The digitization of education has led to the development and use of various educational tools, including lecture slides. These slides have become essential in modern teaching methods as they provide structured information that can be used to create curriculum knowledge graphs. This article explores the benefits and limitations of using lecture slides compared to traditional lecture notes, highlighting any differences in quality between the two approaches. (15)

The structured format of lecture slides contains a clear hierarchies displayed through titles, subtitles, and bullet points. This organized approach facilitates the conversion of information into nodes and relationships within a knowledge graph. And since the slides serve as a condensed representation of a course, it allows for the inclusion of essential points. Doing so helps ensure that crucial aspects of the curriculum are effectively conveyed and captured in the knowledge graph that emerges from it. Also, lecture slides undergo regular updates to reflect the most recent research, statistics, and findings. Educators can provide students with current and relevant information by utilizing a knowledge graph based on this up- dated content.(16)

While lecture slides offer a structured and concise representation of curriculum content, making them a viable data source for constructing knowledge graphs, it's essential to be aware of their limitations. Using lecture slides alone to present complex information and knowledge graphs can be disadvantageous due to several reasons. Firstly, slides are inherently concise, which makes them more suitable for in-class presentations combined with

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verbal explanations. However, when used alone, it is crucial to be aware of the potential loss of crucial context. Secondly, to maintain clarity, complex topics may be simplified on slides, which can result in a lack of depth in the knowledge graph presented. Lastly, the level of detail and structure in educators' slide designs can vary, presenting challenges when integrating information from different sources into a cohesive knowledge graph. Therefore, it is essential to carefully consider the potential drawbacks of constructing slides and ensure that the information presented in the lecture slides aligns with the intended learning outcomes and objectives.(8)

3.2.2 Indexed List of Topics

Utilizing a structured list of topics as the primary input source for academic and research purposes offers a systematic approach to knowledge acquisition and representation. This method organizes topics hierarchically or sequentially, ensuring that a subject matter is covered comprehensively and laying a clear road-map for educators and learners alike. Such a structure can facilitate logical progression in teaching and learning, allowing for building foundational knowledge before progressing to more complex ideas. Moreover, for researchers and curriculum designers, it provides a concise domain overview, enabling the easy identification of core concepts and gaps in the existing literature or syllabus.

However, while the advantages are clear, relying solely on a structured list of topics does have its limitations. The structure that offers clarity can also be restrictive, potentially stifling creative and lateral thinking. There is a risk of oversimplification, as not all knowledge domains lend themselves to a linear or hierarchical breakdown. Additionally, with the context provided by detailed content, there is potential for interpretation and overlooking the nuances and interrelationships between topics. While a structured list of topics serves as an excellent starting point and guide, it is essential to complement it with other resources and teaching methods to ensure a well-rounded understanding of any given subject.

The list is constructed manually and constructing it requires a significant amount of time. There also exists human error as the lists are being constructed manually. Incorrect representation of the course through the list will lead to incorrect TCG of the course.

To achieve our desired structure represented on Figure 3.4, our input list of topics would need to follow the structure represented in Table 3.2.

Using a structured list of topics as the primary input source for constructing a knowledge graph presents many advantages over relying on lecture slides. While lecture slides can be rich in content, they often encompass detailed nuances, specific examples, and design

3.2 Input Source

index	id	subDomain(label)	taxonomy
1	Chapter	label_of_relevant_sub_domain	Bloom_Taxonomy_Level_of_Topic
1.1	Main_Topic	label_of_relevant_sub_domain	Bloom_Taxonomy_Level_of_Topic
1.1.1	Topic	label_of_relevant_sub_domain	Bloom_Taxonomy_Level_of_Topic
1.1.1.1	Sub_Topic	label_of_relevant_sub_domain	Bloom_Taxonomy_Level_of_Topic
1.1.1.1.1	Sub_Topic	label_of_relevant_sub_domain	Bloom_Taxonomy_Level_of_Topic

Table 3.1: Definition of input csv

elements that may need to be more universally representative and scalable. On the other hand, a structured list of topics provides a clear, concise, and consistent framework. Such lists emphasize the core concepts, hierarchies, and relationships vital for building a practical knowledge graph. They reduce the noise and potential inaccuracies from interpreting varied slide formats and designs. Moreover, processing structured lists is computationally more efficient and can be easily standardized across different courses or disciplines. Leveraging structured lists ensures a more streamlined, accurate, and scalable approach to knowledge graph construction, making it a better choice over lecture slides.

3.2.2.1 Definition of Labels of input

- **Index** - The index defines the hierarchy of the listed topics. It helps differentiate between chapters, topics, subtopics and knowledge points.
- **Id** - ID is the unique identifier that describes the topic in discussion. It is crucial to avoid ambiguity in the IDs as they will be loaded directly into RDF and incorrect IDs will lead to incorrect semantic relation between topics.
- **Sub Domain** - Sub domain is an identification label current used for additional information on the topic. This information of the topic should ideally be derived from DBpedia or Wikidata to maintain a semantic label for the topic.
- **Taxonomy** - This defines the Bloom's Taxonomy Level of the topic in the course. This aids for measuring the level of explanation of the topic in the course.

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index	id	subDomain(label)	taxonomy
1	Web	Web Applications	Understand
1.1	Web_Application	Web Applications	Remember
1.2	Web_Foundation	Web Applications	Remember
2	Knowledge_Base	Knowledge Organisation	Understand
2.1	Building_Knowledge_Repositories	Knowledge Organisation	Understand
2.1.1	Manifest_Knowledge	Knowledge Organisation	Understand
2.1.2	Latent_Knowledge	Knowledge Organisation	Understand
2.2	Different_Knowledge_Bases	Knowledge Organisation	Understand
2.2.1	WordNet	Knowledge Organisation	Remember
2.2.2	YAGO	Knowledge Organisation	Remember
2.2.3	FreeBase	Knowledge Organisation	Remember
2.2.4	DBpedia	Knowledge Organisation	Remember
2.2.5	WikiData	Knowledge Organisation	Remember
2.2.6	BabelNet	Knowledge Organisation	Remember
2.3	Knowledge_Base_Languages	Knowledge Organisation	Remember
2.3.1	RDF	Database	Remember
2.3.1.1	RDF_Schema	Database	Remember
2.3.1.2	SPARQL	Database	Remember

Table 3.2: Example Input (template) for TCG

3.3 Construction of TCG

3.3.1 Choosing from Knowledge Graph Schemas

To construct TCG, we employ techniques similar to the construction of a knowledge graphs. The construction of a knowledge graph heavily relies on the design and selection of its schema or ontology. The schema determines the types of entities, their properties, and the relationships within the KG. It plays a crucial role in enhancing its utility, flexibility, and coherence. Therefore, careful consideration should be given when choosing or creating a suitable schema for constructing a KG.

3.3.1.1 Why we need a Schema?

- **Semantic Clarity:** A schema provides clear semantics by defining each entity, property, and relationship. This shared understanding of terms is crucial for collaboration and integrating data from various sources.
- **Data Consistency:** Having a defined schema ensures that data can be added or ingested into the KG consistently. It promotes uniform storage of similar information, minimizing anomalies and inconsistencies.
- **Query Precision:** The use of a schema allows users to have a clear structure of available data when querying the KG. This enhances predictability and precision during data retrieval, enabling more accurate SPARQL queries.
- **Data Validation:** A well-constructed schema serves as a valuable validation tool for new data added to the KG. It enables checking against defined structures and constraints to ensure adherence before incorporation.
- **Reasoning Support:** Knowledge graphs with advanced capabilities can utilize their schema to perform logical reasoning, enabling the deduction of new facts and relationships based on existing information. The schema serves as a foundation for these inference processes.
- **Enhanced Interoperability:** By adopting a standardized schema or building upon existing ontologies, knowledge graphs can greatly improve interoperability between different systems or knowledge graphs, facilitating seamless data exchange.

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- **Domain Modeling:** Fundamentally, a schema represents a specific domain by capturing essential entities and their interactions. This provides domain experts with an invaluable tool for conceptualizing and modeling their area of expertise.

Challenges:

- **Complexity:** Developing a comprehensive schema for diverse or multifaceted domains can be a challenging task, requiring deep domain knowledge and careful consideration of future use cases.
- **Overhead:** While customized schemas provide specificity, they also come with additional costs in terms of design, maintenance, and updates. These activities demand significant time and expertise resources.
- **Inflexibility:** Excessively specific or rigid schemas may constrain adaptability to new information types or changes in the domain. This inflexibility can result in costly revisions or restructuring efforts.
- **Integration Difficulties:** Integrating custom or lesser-known schemas with other systems or knowledge graphs might pose challenges due to limited acceptance and compatibility compared to standard schemas.
- **Semantic Drift:** With time, the meanings and interpretations of certain entities and relationships may evolve. Ensuring that the schema remains semantically consistent and relevant requires ongoing attention.

3.3.1.2 Existing Schemas

There are several schemas that are commonly used in existing Topic Curriculum Graphs (TCGs). TCGs are similar to knowledge graphs, but specifically designed to represent educational curricula and the relationships between various educational concepts. Here are a few schemas used in TCGs:

Subject Schema: This schema represents different subjects or disciplines within an educational curriculum. It includes subject names, identifiers, descriptions, and relationships between subjects, such as prerequisites or dependencies.

Topic Schema: The topic schema focuses on individual topics or subtopics within a subject. It captures information like topic names, descriptions, relationships to other topics, and hierarchical structures. Topics can also have attributes like difficulty level or recommended learning resources.

Competency Schema: This schema describes the competencies or skills that students are expected to acquire within a curriculum. It includes competency names, descriptions, learning objectives, prerequisites, and relationships to other competencies.

Learning Resource Schema: This schema represents various learning resources associated with a curriculum, such as textbooks, online courses, videos, articles, or interactive materials. It includes attributes like resource titles, descriptions, authors, publishers, URLs, and relationships to topics or competencies.

Assessment Schema: The assessment schema captures information about assessments or evaluations associated with a curriculum. It includes attributes like assessment names, types (e.g., exams, quizzes, projects), descriptions, grading criteria, and relationships to competencies or topics.

Prerequisite Schema: This schema represents the prerequisite relationships between different educational concepts. It defines dependencies or required knowledge between subjects, topics, or competencies, helping to establish a sequential order for learning.

Pedagogical Strategy Schema: This schema focuses on different pedagogical strategies employed in teaching specific subjects or topics. It includes information about teaching methods, instructional approaches, or learning techniques associated with particular educational concepts.

It's important to note that the schemas used in TCGs can vary depending on the specific goals, requirements, and design choices of the educational platform or organization implementing the TCG.

3.3.2 Processing

The processing of a structured list of topics is crucial to ensure efficient storage, meaningful visualization, and seamless interoperability. This section outlines the steps involved in processing the data and highlights their significance in enhancing the utility and versatility of the dataset.

Processing a structured list of topics involves verifying course existence, updating topic records, and creating topic connections. These steps ensure efficient storage, reduction of redundancy, and meaningful visualization, while also facilitating interoperability with other datasets and tools. The resulting dataset is more valuable and versatile, making it useful for various academic and organizational purposes.

The first step involves the verification of course existence, which ensures the re-usability of topics and enhances scalability. The matching process seeks matches either by course

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Figure 3.2: Existing Knowledge Graph Schemas

Figure 3.3: Processing Topics for Storage

name or course code. The presence of a match signifies the pre-existence of the course in the database, while its absence necessitates the creation of a new record.

Subsequently, the focus shifts to topic updation. In this step, topics are evaluated, and their presence in the database is verified. If a topic exists in the database and is already linked to the course, no further action is taken. If it exists in the database but not with the course, it's appended to the course. If absent from the database, it's created and then linked to the course.

The third step involves topic connections. In this step, connections between topic pairs are assessed, and new connections are created if they are not already present. This step enhances the relational structure of the data, enabling users to discern patterns and relationships in the dataset. A complete overview of processing the list of topics is seen in Figure 3.3.

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3.3.3 Storage

Representing hierarchical topics in educational and academic domains necessitates a complex relational structure that accurately portrays the depth and breadth of knowledge areas. The Resource Description Framework, a cornerstone of the semantic web, is an ideal choice for depicting such hierarchies. There are several forms of storing this extracted hierarchy; JSON, RDF, Tabular Structure... Consequently, employing RDF to capture these hierarchical structures yields several significant implications. (17) (18)

RDF is renowned for its ability to express intricate and hierarchical relationships semantically within data representation. Unlike conventional tabular formats or JSON structures, RDF relies on subject-predicate-object triples, enabling it to capture raw data and effectively convey interconnections between different pieces of information. Representing complex relationship webs using spreadsheets or CSV files can be burdensome and lead to redundancy. While JSON provides more flexibility than tabular formats, it still faces challenges when dealing with complicated many-to-many relationships or nuanced hierarchies - areas where RDF excels effortlessly. As hierarchical relationships evolve or expand, RDF's extensibility becomes invaluable. In contrast, modifying tabular or JSON formats can be daunting, often leading to changes in schema and compatibility issues.(19)

RDF's interoperability is also worth mentioning. It seamlessly merges with other RDF datasets, providing global scope and fluidity. This is especially important when integrating multiple hierarchical topics or expanding a knowledge base. Merging or combining unique schemas of JSON or tabular structures often requires extensive manual effort.

Integrating RDF with ontology languages like OWL allows for automated reasoning, providing the ability to infer new relationships or facts within dynamically evolving hierarchies. Tabular and JSON formats lack native support for reasoning capabilities, requiring external processing to make inferences or deductions. Regarding querying, RDF is equipped with SPARQL—a standardized query language explicitly designed for RDF. SPARQL ensures a uniform and comprehensive access mechanism regardless of underlying storage nuances or hierarchy specifics. In comparison, while SQL caters to tabular data and various tools exist for JSON querying, the semantic depth and breadth offered by SPARQL remain unparalleled.

RDF serves as a decentralized and linked data solution in the vast interconnected web. It goes beyond merely storing information by interconnecting it and making it accessible within the broader Linked Data ecosystem. Unlike tabular and JSON formats, which

are web-friendly but lack inherent features of decentralization and linking, RDF excels in representing complex hierarchical topics with intricate relationships.(20)

Conclusively, when faced with representing and storing such hierarchies, choosing RDF is not just an option but the optimal choice. While tabular and JSON formats have their strengths, RDF's emphasis on semantics, adaptability, and interconnectedness positions it as a frontrunner for handling specialized tasks.

3.3.3.1 RDF Structure

A well-designed hierarchical framework is crucial for organizing and comprehending knowledge in academic fields. It should effectively capture the complex relationships between topics, sub-domains, and domains. When developing a data structure to store such extensive information, there are several essential requirements to consider.

Taxonomy Hierarchy: An essential aspect of academic content organization is the incorporation of Bloom's Taxonomy Levels. The provided structure effectively outlines these levels, ranging from "Remember" to "Create," establishing a continuum of cognitive complexity. This hierarchical representation is crucial for comprehending the extent to which a specific topic or course delves into various depths of knowledge and thinking skills.

Topic Specificity with Course Alignment: Topics are essential components of educational modules, serving as the foundation upon which learning is built. Therefore, it is crucial for a structure to not only organize individual topics but also connect them to relevant courses. In our proposed structure, we observe that topics such as "Evaluation" or "Fairness" are clearly defined and linked with specific courses and their corresponding levels in Bloom's taxonomy. This comprehensive approach provides a detailed overview of the academic landscape related to each topic.

Course Metadata: Courses are complex structures with various components, including metadata such as the course name, code, and related sub-domains. Establishing a connection between a course and its main topic or focus area is also beneficial to enhance the understanding of its overall theme more efficiently.

Sub-domain Connectivity: At a deeper level, sub-domains play a role in categorizing and connecting various topics and courses. A clear structure should effectively represent each sub-domain and its relationship to its larger domain. For example, linking "Parallel Computing" as a sub-domain within the broader "Computer Science" domain ensures that knowledge is contextualized.

Domain Representation: The domain, such as "Computer Science" or any other field, is at the top of the hierarchy. This level provides a broad context and allows for potential

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Figure 3.4: RDF Structure of Topics

connections across different domains, promoting a transdisciplinary perspective.

Uniform Resource Identifiers: Using URIs, like in the ‘@prefix’ declaration, ensures that the structure is not limited to local datasets but also integrated with global datasets. These identifiers give each data point a unique global reference and facilitate linked open data ecosystems.

In summary, creating a hierarchical arrangement of topics requires a clear hierarchy, precise alignment between topics and courses, comprehensive course metadata, and seamless connections between sub-domains and domains. Global identifiers are crucial for capturing academic content effectively in RDF format while maintaining its richness and depth. The structure of a topics and courses stored as RDF can be seen in figure 3.4 and 3.5.

3.3.4 Visualization

The Resource Description Framework (RDF) inherently captures relationships and structures in a way conducive to graph-based representations. While RDF data, in its raw form, can be challenging to decipher and analyze, visual tools transform it into an understandable and intuitive format, allowing for quick insights and facilitating a deeper understanding.

Choosing to represent RDF data as a graph offers an unparalleled advantage. With their nodes and edges, graphs naturally represent entities and their interrelationships. Given that RDF data emphasizes relationships—linking subjects, predicates, and objects—a graph visualization aligns perfectly with its structural essence. The representation is not just about aesthetics; by visualizing RDF as a graph, we are leveraging a representation that resonates with the data’s inherent structure, making it more comprehensible(21).

Figure 3.5: RDF Structure of Courses, Subdomains and Domains

Interactive visualizations elevate this comprehension to another level. Zooming into specific nodes, exploring adjacent relationships, or tracing paths between topics allows users to engage with the data dynamically. It lets them ask questions, seek patterns, or dive deep into specific areas of interest. Interaction transforms a static representation into a live, query-able interface, maximizing the utility of the visualization.

Incorporating hierarchy into the visualization enhances its interpretative power. By varying node sizes or using directed edges, we can signify the importance or flow of information. The size aids in immediately recognizing key nodes or primary topics and their subtopics. Such a representation acknowledges the natural hierarchy in many datasets, especially educational ones, where topics can have sub-topics.

Lastly, the ability to distinctly identify parent and child nodes is vital. This not only preserves the data's inherent structure but also provides a clear path of derivation or flow. Knowing where a particular piece of information stems from (its parent) or what it leads to (its child nodes) creates a road-map for understanding the topic's placement within the broader context(21).

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3.4 TCG Operation

TCG provides a CRUD (Create, Read, Update, and Delete) operations that enable not only the creation of knowledge but also its updating and deletion. By catering specifically to nodes (entities or topics) and their inter-relations (links), these operations support the fluidity and evolution of knowledge, ensuring that our TCG remains current, relevant, and continually evolving. In this section, we delve into the significance of these operations and their unique importance for nodes and links.(22)

The fluidity and evolution of knowledge requires a wide array of operations that allow for the creation of new nodes and links, updating existing ones, or removing irrelevant ones. The inclusion of these operations ensures that our KG remains comprehensive, up-to-date, and relevant. Knowledge domains often overlap, and a topic in one domain might be relevant in another. Therefore, it is essential to have robust operations when establishing or severing links between topics or when updating the relevance or details of a node.

3.4.1 Create

In the context of nodes, the Create operation plays a crucial role in facilitating the addition of new topics or entities to the system. By employing this operation, we can effectively incorporate emerging concepts into the Graph, thereby ensuring its comprehensiveness and currency. The ability to create fresh additions of topics within the graph offers enhanced flexibility in modifying course content as well as completing knowledge representations.

To create a node, we require the below information of the topic.

- Unique ID
- Name
- Sub Domain Label
- Course
- Taxonomy Level

The definition for each of these can be seen in section 3.2.2.1

For links, the Create operation reflects the intricate web of knowledge where concepts are interlinked, providing context and depth to topics. It helps to establish the relationship between topics and to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the knowledge domain. Any two unlinked nodes should be link-able once they are selected.

The creation of nodes and links are queried in SPARQL and updated in the RDF Store dominantly through `INSERT DATA {...}` command.

3.4.2 Read

The Read operation for nodes provides users with insights about a specific topic, its properties, and its relevance in the broader knowledge domain. It allows users to gain a deeper understanding of the topic and its context. And for links, the Read operation offers insights into how two topics are connected, providing a richer, more contextual understanding. It helps to provide a more detailed understanding of the knowledge domain. The nodes and links can be queried to read using `SELECT WHERE {...}` command.

3.4.3 Update

The Update operation ensures the accuracy of the data and ensures that the system remains accurate and relevant. For instance, a topic that initially had minimal relevance in a course might later become a central concept. Updating caters to such shifts. The Update operation ensures that the links remain accurate and relevant, providing a more comprehensive and accurate understanding of the knowledge domain. As our understanding deepens, the way two topics relate might shift.

Since SPARQL does not explicitly provide an update option, we will read the existing data on the node and links, delete and recreate the item with specific changes. We SPARQL query this using

```
SELECT WHERE{
  ...
}
DELETE WHERE {
  ...
}
INSERT DATA {
  ...
}
```

3.4.4 Delete

The Delete operation allows educators or system managers to curate course content without risking the loss of global knowledge. It ensures flexibility in course design while maintaining

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the integrity of the KG. The Delete operation ensures that the KG remains accurate and relevant by severing connections that are no longer needed.

We can delete links and nodes using `DELETE WHERE {...}` SPARQL query. We must ensure that the node deletion does not inherently delete the node from the database but removes it from the course.

3.5 Assessing Course Objective

Curricular design offers numerous advantages in the educational setting. It provides educators and students with a comprehensive understanding of the fundamental elements of a course, thereby enhancing the learning experience. One promising solution that has gained considerable attention is Topic Curriculum Graphs, which are centered around specific topics. This report examines the process of designing, implementing, and exploring the implications of this approach in detail. An educational graph provides a practical and important reference for revealing the law of dynamic development in the field of knowledge (23).

Using the RDF structure mentioned in figure 3.4 and 3.5, the course objective can be computed by statistical data of Bloom's Taxonomy Level of topics for their respective SubDomains. This provides the exact definition of the course and can easily aid educators in designing a curriculum that aligns with the desired learning outcomes. In addition, an educational graph describes the logical relationship between each entity in the curriculum system, enabling educators to understand the dependencies of different knowledge points and teaching resources. This understanding of interconnections and dependencies allows educators to design a curriculum that promotes a more holistic and comprehensive learning experience for students. Moreover, an educational graph serves as a valuable tool for facilitating the efficient utilization of subject knowledge (24).

4

Implementation

4.1 Construction of TCG

4.1.1 Schema

In Topic Curriculum Graphs, the **Topic Schema** stands out as a highly effective schema for several reasons. Education fundamentally revolves around topics, whether in a school, university, or any learning platform. Topics are the foundation for learning by connecting abstract subjects to concrete competencies.

Granular Representation: Any identified topic is linked to a specific sub-domain and course. This detail ensures that topics are well-defined, contextualized, and easily navigable within the curriculum system.

Hierarchical Connectivity: Topics in a curriculum have a hierarchical and interconnected structure. Some topics are prerequisites for others, while others are part of larger modules or foundational for specific competencies. The Topic Schema captures these connections and reflects the hierarchy.

Intuitive Organization: A curriculum follows a tiered structure with subjects at the top, followed by topics and sub-topics. This progression mirrors natural learning, introducing broader concepts before diving into specific details. The Topic Schema is designed to reflect this organization within the curriculum system intuitively.

Integration: One of the key strengths of a Topic Schema is its ability to seamlessly integrate with other existing schemas, allowing it to become part of a more extensive knowledge framework. For example, when tethered to the Competency Schema, the Topic Schema can demonstrate how theoretical topics translate into real-world skills. Additionally, integration with the Learning Resource Schema enables learners to access resources directly related to specific topics and enhances their learning experience.

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Interdisciplinary Learning: In today’s academic landscape, subjects and topics often intersect rather than being isolated. Utilizing a robust Topic Schema that integrates well with Subject and Prerequisite Schemas can highlight these intersections effectively, encouraging interdisciplinary learning opportunities and promoting holistic understanding among students.

All schemas are essential in constructing a TCG, but the Topic Schema holds a central position within the educational framework. Its comprehensive depiction of topics, ability to capture hierarchical structures, and exceptional adaptability make it an optimal choice for representing curricula in today’s digital era.

4.1.2 Upload Input Data

Processing input data is a crucial part of any digital platform. In this section, we will discuss how input data, especially in the form of CSV files, is efficiently managed and integrated into the existing TCG system.

The significance of input data handling cannot be overstated. Proper data validation and processing provide feedback to the users, guiding them in providing the correct information. In addition, streamlined input data processing allows for easier integration of additional data in the future. It ensures that the data being entered matches the expected format and maintains the integrity of the underlying databases.

To facilitate the addition of new courses via CSV files, a dedicated web interface is provided. This interface is crafted using Bootstrap for responsiveness and is designed with the following form fields: Course Name, Course Code, and CSV File. Upon filling out this form and selecting a CSV file, the data within can be processed by clicking the ‘Upload’ button shown in Figure 5.1.

4.1.3 Processing

On triggering the upload action, the CSV file undergoes rigorous processing. The system first ensures a CSV file is selected. The contents of the file are read, and rows of data are identified. For each row, it’s broken down into its constituent columns to extract data points such as topics, subdomains, and taxonomy levels. The preprocessing follows the design laid out in Figure 3.3.

A parent-child map is constructed to identify relationships between different topics. Root topics (main topics) and their respective sub-topics are mapped. After parsing, the system compares the subdomains from the uploaded CSV against those already present in the

system. Unmatched subdomains (those not present in the system) are isolated for further processing. Unmatched subdomains are then added to the system, with their name and IDs properly formatted for consistency.

Before adding the course, the system checks if it already exists. If it doesn't, the course, along with its associated subdomains and root topics, is added. For each topic in the CSV, the system first checks if the node (topic) is already part of the course. If it is, a warning is issued. If the node exists but not in the course, it is linked to the course with its taxonomy level. If the node doesn't exist at all, it's created and linked to its respective subdomain and course.

Using the previously built parent-child map, parent nodes are connected to their child nodes, establishing relationships. Upon successful addition and mapping, the user is redirected to a confirmation page or a relevant interface showing the newly added course details.

In conclusion, the careful orchestration of the data processing steps ensures not only the preservation of data consistency but also streamlines the addition of new information to the system. As the system evolves, such a structured approach to data input will prove instrumental in maintaining a robust TCG that is easily scalable.

4.2 Storage

We use Apache Jena Fuseki as our RDF Triplestore for managing our data. Apache Jena Fuseki is an open-source SPARQL server that provides an HTTP interface to SPARQL 1.1 Query, Update, and Graph Store HTTP Protocol. At its core, Fuseki is designed to serve datasets as web resources by adhering to the standards and protocols of the semantic web community (25).

Using Apache Jena Fuseki as the RDF store in the presented system ensures that the extracted topics and hierarchical arrangements can be efficiently stored, retrieved, and managed. As the system extracts knowledge from the documents and processes them into a structured format, it becomes essential to have a reliable and scalable storage solution.

At its core, Fuseki is renowned for handling complex relational data, making it apt for representing the intertwined nature of academic courses. Semantic databases offer advantages in representing complex relationships and hierarchies, characteristic of course structures. Apache Jena Fuseki stands out with its dedicated SPARQL server in this context. SPARQL is the query language for RDF databases, designed for precisely querying and extracting data from semantic graphs.(26)

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4.2.1 Key Features

HTTP Server: Fuseki runs as a standalone HTTP server, which means it can be easily integrated with web services, making RDF data readily accessible over the web.

SPARQL Endpoints: Fuseki provides both read and write SPARQL endpoints, making it flexible for varied application requirements, from data retrieval to graph updates.

Web User Interface: For management and monitoring, Fuseki offers a web-based user interface that allows users to manage datasets, monitor server activity, and directly execute SPARQL queries.

Dataset Management: Fuseki supports in-memory and persistent storage databases, ensuring that RDF data can be managed efficiently, irrespective of volume.

4.2.2 Advantages over different RDF Store

Fuseki's standalone HTTP server which allows for easy integration with web services, allows for a quick and easy communication with the RDF data. And coupled with its ease of installation makes Fuseki an easy choice. Granted several other RDF stores such as Neo4j also can achieve the same functionality and has more operations for complex problems, we find that Apache Jena Fuseki to meet our demands, or requests.

4.3 Graph Visualization

Using modern visualization techniques, the TCG Visualization offers a compelling representation of the curriculum structure. Rooted in the principles of data visualization, the graph provides a quick overview of the curriculum's composition and the relationships between different topics.

4.3.1 Data Fetching

In our exploration of creating a TCG for academic courses, the key challenge was sourcing and structuring data. We employed Apache Jena Fuseki's database system for this purpose.

Fetching data for a course from the server involves several steps. It starts with a request to the server's endpoint, which triggers the data retrieval process. This endpoint is designed to respond to queries with an appropriate course ID. We setup our endpoint on Jena on `/query/data`.

Once the endpoint is triggered, several SPARQL queries are formulated for various purposes. These queries are designed to fetch course-specific nodes with the average taxonomy

4.3 Graph Visualization

value and degree. They also gather topics associated with the specified course, relationships or links between the topics, and domain and subdomain details. Additionally, they collect details about the course and information related to Bloom's Taxonomy Levels associated with the course content.

Additionally we compute a degree based on the number of children nodes and taxonomy. This degree is used for sizing and colouring of the nodes. The formula to calculate the degree, based on the average taxonomy value, is given by:

$$\text{degree} = e^{(\text{avgTaxonomyValueOfChildren} \times \log(2))}$$

We can extract all nodes relevant to the course using the below SPARQL Query. This SPARQL query retrieves details about specific nodes, likely topics or taxonomies, from a designated course. It selects each node's ID, name, associated subdomains, and computes an average value from the related Bloom's taxonomy level, as well as a derived mathematical degree. The query is crafted to exclude nodes categorized as courses, subdomains, or domains, ensuring only relevant details are fetched. All results are then grouped by node ID and name, and ordered by the ID for structured presentation.

```
const nodesQuery = `
PREFIX ex: <http://localhost:8080/>
PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
PREFIX math: <http://www.w3.org/2005/xpath-functions/math#>

SELECT ?id ?name (GROUP_CONCAT(DISTINCT ?subDomain;separator=", ") as
    ?subDomains) (AVG(?taxonomyValue) AS
    ?avgTaxonomyValue) (math:exp(AVG(?taxonomyValue)
    * math:log(2)) AS ?degree) WHERE {
    ?id ex:name ?name .
    ?id ex:sub_domain ?subDomain .
    ?id ex:in_course/ex:course ?course .
    ?id ex:in_course/ex:bloom_taxonomy_level ?btl .
    ?btl ex:value ?taxonomyValueRaw .
    BIND(xsd:decimal(?taxonomyValueRaw) AS ?taxonomyValue)
    FILTER (?course = ex:Course${course})
    FILTER NOT EXISTS { ?id a ex:Course }
    FILTER NOT EXISTS { ?id a ex:SubDomain }
    FILTER NOT EXISTS { ?id a ex:Domain }
}
```

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```
GROUP BY ?id ?name
ORDER BY ?id
‘;
```

We can then extract the relation between each nodes by the below SPARQL Query. This query retrieves relationships between topics within a given course. Specifically, it identifies pairs of topics (?source and ?target) where the ?source topic has a relationship with the ?target topic, and both belong to the specified course. The linksQuery is designed to identify relationships or "links" between various topics in a course. Each topic (identified as ?source) in the database is checked to determine if it's linked to another topic (?target). Only those pairs of topics that belong to the specified course are selected for the results.

```
const linksQuery = ‘
PREFIX ex: <http://localhost:8080/>
SELECT ?source ?target WHERE {
  ?source a ex:Topic ;
    ex:in_course/ex:course ?course ;
    ex:has_topics ?target .

  ?target ex:in_course/ex:course ?course .

FILTER (?course = ex:Course${course})
}
‘;
```

We will also extract all the existing subdomains using the subdomainQuery. This query fetches all nodes that are classified under the category "SubDomain". For each such node, its identifier (?id) and name (?name) are retrieved. The subdomainQuery delves into the database to fetch a list of all subdomains. A subdomain, in this context, can be understood as a subset or specialization within a larger domain of knowledge. For each subdomain, its unique identifier and name are captured.

```
const subdomainQuery = ‘
PREFIX ex: <http://localhost:8080/>
SELECT ?id ?name WHERE {
  ?id a ex:SubDomain ;
    ex:name ?name .
}
```

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```
}  
';
```

Similar to the subdomain query, this one fetches all nodes classified under the category "Domain" and retrieves their identifiers and names. The `domainQuery` provides a holistic view of broader fields or areas of knowledge known as domains. Each domain's unique identifier and name are extracted for reference. Domains typically encapsulate various subdomains, offering a hierarchical view of knowledge.

```
const domainQuery = '  
PREFIX ex: <http://localhost:8080/>  
SELECT ?id ?name WHERE {  
    ?id a ex:Domain ;  
        ex:name ?name .  
}  
';
```

We then extract information of the courses using a `courseQuery`. It retrieves the identifier, name, course code, and the root topic of the course, given a course identifier. The `courseQuery` is crafted to provide details about a specific academic course. When provided with a course's unique identifier, it extracts essential details such as its name, associated course code, and the primary or "root" topic associated with that course.

```
const courseQuery = '  
PREFIX ex: <http://localhost:8080/>  
SELECT ?id ?name ?code ?root_topic WHERE {  
    ?id a ex:Course ;  
        ex:name ?name ;  
        ex:course_code ?code ;  
        ex:root_topic ?root_topic .  
    FILTER (?id = ex:Course${course})  
}  
';
```

We then fetch nodes that are categorized under "BloomTaxonomyLevel". The Bloom's taxonomy levels are a set of hierarchical models used to classify educational learning objectives. For each such level, the query retrieves its identifier, name, and value. The `bloomTLQuery` dives into the Bloom's Taxonomy Levels, a renowned classification system

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in education that defines levels of intellectual behavior essential to learning. This query fetches every level's unique identifier, its descriptive name, and a specific value associated with it, which might be indicative of its position or weight in the hierarchy.

```
const bloomTLQuery = `
PREFIX ex: <http://localhost:8080/>
SELECT ?id ?name ?value WHERE {
  ?id a ex:BloomTaxonomyLevel ;
      ex:name ?name ;
      ex:value ?value .
}
`;
```

Utilizing the `node-fetch` module, each SPARQL query is asynchronously executed against the Fuseki server's endpoint. The method of choice is POST due to the complex nature of SPARQL queries, and the 'Content-Type' is set to 'application/SPARQL-query' to appropriately handle SPARQL requests.

Once the queries are executed, each query response is parsed from a JSON format. This parsing extracts data, including topics, links between topics, subdomains, domains, course details, and Bloom's Taxonomy Levels. Furthermore, URI-specific adjustments are performed on the IDs to make them more accessible (e.g., stripping out the base 'http://localhost:8080/').

Finally, the processed data is aggregated into a unified JSON structure comprising nodes, links, subdomains, domains, course specifics, and Bloom's Taxonomy Levels. Frontend components or other services can then use this structured data to visualize or process the course graph.

4.3.2 Visualization Techniques

Nodes in this visualization represent individual topics or subjects in the curriculum. When clicked, their properties, such as id, name, and subdomains, are fetched and displayed in the update modal. Their color is determined based on their degree (i.e., their connections or importance in the graph), offering a visual distinction for more central or connected nodes.

Each node, encapsulated as a circle in an SVG container, is visually characterized by its 'degree.' The circle's radius is proportionate to this degree, offering an immediate visual

cue about its relative significance or connectivity within the network. Distinctively, nodes identified as the 'root topic' are accentuated with an orange stroke, distinguishing them from the standard nodes that bear a white stroke.

Interactivity:

Interactivity is pivotal in our visualization, facilitating user engagement and more profound insights. The nodes have a dragging behavior, allowing users to rearrange them interactively within the canvas. Mouse events are incorporated to augment the user's exploration:

- **Hovering:** On hovering over a node, non-neighboring nodes, their labels, and unrelated links are dimmed. This action underscores the connections of the selected node, aiding users in tracing relational pathways and understanding context.

- **Clicking:** A more intricate behavior is tied to the click event. When a node is clicked while holding the Ctrl or Cmd key, it toggles its 'selection' state. Selected nodes are visually differentiated with a black stroke and a glow effect. This mechanism permits users to earmark specific nodes of interest, likely serving a more considerable analytical function in the system. Subsequent functions, such as 'processSelectedNodes,' suggest further processing or analysis tied to these selections.

Labeling:

Accompanying each node is its label, derived from the node's name, positioned slightly to its right. The labels are designed to be non-interactive, ensuring they do not obstruct or interfere with node interactions. They are vertically aligned to the middle of their respective nodes for consistency and clarity.

```
const node = svg.append("g")
  .attr("stroke-width", 1.5)
  .selectAll("circle")
  .data(graph.nodes)
  .join("circle")
  .attr("r", (d) => nodeRadiusScale(+d.degree))
  .attr("stroke", d => rootNodes.includes(d.id) ? "orange" : "#fff")
  .attr("fill", color)
  .style("filter", d => rootNodes.includes(d.id) ? "url(#redGlow)":null)
  .call(drag(simulation))
  .on("mouseover", function (d) {
    node.filter(nd => !_.includes(nodeNeighbors[d.id], nd.id))
      .style("opacity", 0.1);
    label.filter(ld => !_.includes(nodeNeighbors[d.id], ld.id))
      .style("opacity", 0.1);
```

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```
link.filter(lkd => !((lkd.source.id == d.id) ||
                    (lkd.target.id == d.id)))
                    .style("opacity", 0.1);
})
.on("mouseout", function (d) {
  node.style("opacity", null);
  label.style("opacity", null);
  link.style("opacity", null);
})
```

Links represent relationships or connections between these topics. They can be dynamically added or removed, reflecting how topics are interrelated within the curriculum. In our visualization system, these connections, or "links", are depicted as lines connecting nodes. Alongside, we introduce mechanisms to understand node connectivity within the graph structure.

Link Visualization: Every link in the graph is represented as a line segment in the SVG container. The visual characteristics of these links are uniform - a consistent stroke color ("#999") and a fixed opacity (0.6). However, each line's thickness, or 'stroke width,' varies. This variance is determined by each link's 'weight' attribute, mapped using the `linkStrokeScale` function. Such a design decision implies that links with greater weight values would be rendered thicker, offering a direct visual insight into each connection's relative significance or intensity.

Node Connectivity Mechanisms: A pertinent challenge in graph visualization is discerning a node's immediate neighbors or connections. To tackle this, a data structure, `nodeNeighbors`, has been constructed. For every node in the graph, this structure captures a list of its neighboring nodes - directly connected via links; to simplify search operations when highlighting or interacting with neighboring nodes and enable efficient computations for subsequent analytical or visualization functions that necessitate knowledge about node neighbors.

```
const link = svg.append("g")
  .attr("stroke", "#999")
  .attr("stroke-opacity", 0.6)
  .selectAll("line")
  .data(graph.links)
  .join("line")
  .attr("stroke-width", d => linkStrokeScale(+d.weight));
```

4.3.3 Understanding Heirarchy

A distinctive feature of the visualization is how it denotes hierarchy and importance:

Colour Variation: The varying colors of the nodes signify their importance or centrality in the curriculum. A gradient color scheme is used, where specific colors might correspond to topics of higher importance or centrality, guiding the viewer's attention to key areas in the curriculum.

Node Size: The size of the nodes, determined by their degree, gives a visual cue about the topic's relevance. Larger nodes suggest a topic with many connections, making it a pivotal or foundational subject in the curriculum.

In essence, this visualization not only presents the curriculum structure but also offers intuitive cues about the significance and relationships of different topics through color and size variations. It is a blend of design and functionality, ensuring users get a macro and micro perspective of the curriculum's landscape.

4.4 TCG Operations

4.4.1 Create

The ability to dynamically add nodes is essential in developing our graph visualization system. This section outlines the processes associated with this node addition mechanism from the client and server perspectives.

Client-Side Request Formation:

We call a `nodeAddition` function to send a POST request with critical components of the node: ID, name, course, sub-domain, and BTL (Bloom Taxonomy Level). An asynchronous fetch request targets the server endpoint `/add/node`. The request is configured to have headers set to `'Content-Type': 'application/json'` and to contain the node's attributes in the request body as a JSON object. This action is performed at the `server/update` server end point as it requires inserting data and updating the server.

Server-Side Node Addition:

Upon receiving the request on the `/add/node` route, the server extracts node attributes from the request body. We then construct a SPARQL INSERT DATA query tailored to add a new node with the provided attributes in the graph database. Subsequently, another asynchronous fetch request is dispatched, targeting a SPARQL endpoint. This

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request attempts to execute the previously constructed query, pushing the new node's data into the graph database.

Response Handling:

If the SPARQL endpoint acknowledges the insertion and responds positively, the server logs a successful message and sends a JSON response to the client, indicating a successful addition. If the insertion attempt is unsuccessful, the server retrieves the error message from the SPARQL endpoint's response, logs it, and sends a structured JSON response back to the client. This response comprises the failure status and the associated error message.

Client-Side Confirmation:

Back on the client side, in the `nodeAddition` function, the server's response is awaited and parsed. In case of success, a message is logged, and a confirmation popup is presented to the user. The corresponding message is logged if there's an error or failure, indicating the node addition's unsuccessful attempt.

A pseudo code can be seen below.

```
FUNCTION nodeAddition(nodeID, nodeName, nodeCourse, nodeSubDomain, nodeBTL)
1. Try
  a. Set headers for a POST request with content type as 'application/json'
  b. Send an asynchronous POST request to '/add/node' with the provided
      node attributes as JSON
  c. Await and parse the server response to JSON
  d. If the server indicates successful addition:
    i. Log a success message
    ii. Show a confirmation message to the user
    iii. Return true
  e. Else, log the server's error message and return false
2. Catch any errors, log them as failures, and return false
END FUNCTION
```

```
SERVER-SIDE Query for '/add/node' route
const addQuery = '
PREFIX ex: <http://localhost:8080/>
INSERT DATA {
  ex:${req.body.id} a ex:Topic ;
  ex:name "${req.body.name}" ;
  ex:sub_domain ex:${req.body.subDomain} ;
  ex:in_course [
```

```

        ex:course ex:${req.body.course} ;
        ex:bloom_taxonomy_level ex:${req.body.btl}
    ] .
}
';

```

4.4.2 Read

By using the read operation, you can access and view the information stored in our graph. This is especially useful when you need to retrieve specific data points or analyze patterns and relationships within the graph. In this way, the read operation can help you gain insights into your data, and make better-informed decisions. To increase the usability of the graph, we will opt to fill out fields with existing information of the node to make it easier for intended operations; like updating a node.

Retrieving detailed information about a specific node in the graph is another pivotal functionality within our system. This process entails fetching general attributes, associated courses, and parent and child nodes. We utilise a `getNodeInfo` function. This action is performed at the `server/query` server end point as it only requires querying to gather information on the node.

```

FUNCTION getNodeInfo(node)
1. Send an asynchronous GET request to '/node/details' with the node's ID
    as a parameter
2. Await and parse the server response to JSON
3. Log the data received
4. Return the parsed data
END FUNCTION

```

```

SERVER-SIDE Query for '/node/details' route
const courseInfo = `
PREFIX ex: <http://localhost:8080/>
SELECT
  (REPLACE(STR(?course), "http://localhost:8080/", "") as ?courseStr)
  (REPLACE(STR(?btl), "http://localhost:8080/", "") as ?btlStr)
WHERE {
  ex:${nodeId} ex:in_course ?inCourseNode .
  ?inCourseNode ex:course ?course ;

```

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```
        ex:bloom_taxonomy_level ?bt1 .
    }
    ‘;

    const generalInfo = ‘
    PREFIX ex: <http://localhost:8080/>
    SELECT ?id ?name ?subDomain WHERE{
        ?id a ex:Topic;
        ex:name ?name;
        ex:sub_domain ?subDomain
        FILTER (?id = ex:${nodeId})
    }
    ‘;

    const parentInfo = ‘
    PREFIX ex: <http://localhost:8080/>
    SELECT ?id WHERE{
        ?id a ex:Topic;
        ex:has_topics ex:${nodeId} .
        ex:${nodeId} a ex:Topic .
    }
    ‘;

    const childrenInfo = ‘
    PREFIX ex: <http://localhost:8080/>
    SELECT ?topics WHERE{
        ex:${nodeId} a ex:Topic;
        ex:has_topics ?topics .
        ?topics a ex:Topic .
    }
    ‘;
```

The `getNodeInfo` function, when invoked, sends a GET request to the `/node/details` endpoint. The node’s ID passed to this function is added as a query parameter. This request signifies the client’s intent to fetch all pertinent details related to the node specified.

The server receives the request on the `/node/details` route and retrieves the node’s ID from the query parameters. Four SPARQL queries are formulated:

- `generalInfo` fetches basic details such as the node's name and sub-domain.
- `courseInfo` gathers details about courses related to the node.
- `parentInfo` identifies parent nodes that are linked to the specified node.
- `childrenInfo` discovers child nodes that the specified node points to.

Each query is then executed asynchronously against the SPARQL endpoint.

Data Aggregation and Response Formation: The server awaits responses for each executed SPARQL query, parses them, and then structures the data in an easily consumable format. The server processes the received data to eliminate prefixes and present a cleaner version of the node's attributes. The resulting structured data, which consists of general node details, associated courses, parent nodes, and child nodes, is then packed into a comprehensive JSON object.

Back in the `getNodeInfo` function, the server's response is awaited and parsed. This parsed data is logged for verification purposes and then returned, making it available for further processing or rendering on the client side.

4.4.3 Update

Updating a node in a graph involves not just changing the node itself, but often also adjusting its connections or relationships with other nodes. This process can be complex, as it necessitates the seamless synchronization of deletions, additions, and the maintenance of relationships to ensure the graph's integrity. Here we delve into the mechanism of node updating, analyzing both the client-side and server-side procedures.

Since RDFs don't explicitly offer a method to update triples, we update them by reading information, storing it in chace, deleting triples and then re-creating triples. This action is performed at the `server/query` and `server/update` server end point as it requires querying to gather information on the node and inserting and removing data to and from the database.

```
FUNCTION sendSparqlUpdateQuery
1. Extract values from input fields
2. Fetch the existing details of the node intended for modification
3. Delete the existing node
4. Add the modified node
5. Restore the relationships (with parents, children, and associated courses)
6. Notify the user and refresh the page
```

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```
END FUNCTION
```

```
SERVER-SIDE Query for '/add/course-to-node' route
```

```
const addQuery = '  
PREFIX ex: <http://localhost:8080/>  
INSERT DATA {  
  ex:${nodeId} ex:in_course [  
    ex:course ex:${courseCode};  
    ex:bloom_taxonomy_level ex:${newBTL}  
  ] .  
}  
';
```

```
SERVER-SIDE FUNCTION for '/delete/node' route
```

```
const deleteQuery = '  
PREFIX ex: <http://localhost:8080/>  
DELETE WHERE {  
  ex:${nodeId} ?p ?o .  
};  
DELETE WHERE {  
  ?s ?p1 ex:${nodeId} .  
};  
DELETE WHERE {  
  ?s2 ex:has_topics ex:${nodeId} .  
}  
';
```

The initiation of the update process starts on the client side, triggered by the function `sendSparqlUpdateQuery`. This function first extracts the new values from various input fields, capturing the user's desired updates. Following this extraction, it retrieves the current details of the node intended for modification using the `getNodeInfo` function. A crucial step that follows is the deletion of the original node, carried out by the `nodeDeletion` function. Subsequently, the updated node is added back into the graph via the `nodeAddition` function. However, the addition of the node only forms part of the task. Maintaining this node's relationships is paramount, primarily if the graph database supports intricate

connections. To cater to this, parent nodes of the updated node are reconnected using the `connectNodes` function. Similarly, child nodes are re-associated using the same function. Lastly, courses initially linked with the node are re-associated. This is achieved by the `addCourseAndBTLToNode` function, with a caveat: any course currently being updated is skipped since it was addressed during the addition of the new node. When the function `addCourseAndBTLToNode` is called on the server side, the route `/add/course-to-node` is invoked. This route extracts relevant details from the request, and a SPARQL query is formulated. This query aims to link the given course to the node effectively. Once executed, the server responds, indicating the success or potential failure of the operation. Deletion of the node, an operation critical to the update process, is routed through the server endpoint `/delete/node`. Here, the server first discerns the node's ID from the incoming request. Subsequently, a comprehensive SPARQL delete query is structured to obliterate the node and any linked relationships from the graph. Following its execution, a response indicating the outcome—success or failure—is dispatched to the client. Concluding the update process on the client side, the function `sendSparqlUpdateQuery` prompts the user with a confirmation dialog. This dialog informs the user of the successful update of the node. As a finishing touch, the page is refreshed, providing a visual representation of the updated graph.

4.4.4 Delete

4.4.4.1 Delete Node from RDF Store

In a graph-based environment, erasing a node isn't just about eliminating that individual entity. It's about ensuring that connections, references, and associations linked to that node are also gracefully managed to preserve data integrity. This action is performed at the `server/update` server end point as it requires inserting data and updating the server.

```
const deleteQuery = `
  PREFIX ex: <http://localhost:8080/>
  DELETE WHERE {
    ex:${nodeId} ?p ?o .
  };
  DELETE WHERE {
    ?s ?p1 ex:${nodeId} .
  };
  DELETE WHERE {
```

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```
?s2 ex:has_topics ex:${nodeId} .  
}  
';
```

```
If deletion is successful:  
    Send success response  
Else:  
    Send failure response
```

```
Function nodeDeletion(nodeID):  
    response <- send POST request to '/delete/node' with nodeID  
  
    If response indicates success:  
        Log success message  
        Return true  
    Else:  
        Handle root node or other deletion errors  
        Return false
```

The server-side route `/delete/node` serves this exact purpose. Upon invocation, the node's ID is discerned from the incoming request. A preliminary check is conducted (though it's commented out in the provided code) to identify if the targeted node is a root node of a course. If such is the case, an immediate response is dispatched, stating that root nodes cannot be deleted.

Following this check, a SPARQL query is constructed to expunge the node from the graph database. The query targets not just the node but also its various associations. After the successful execution of this query, a response is relayed back to the client side, informing about the outcome.

On the client side, the function `nodeDeletion` interfaces with the aforementioned server route. It prepares and sends the deletion request and subsequently processes the response. If the deletion is successful, a confirmation is logged; otherwise, the user is alerted if they attempted to delete a root node.

4.4.4.2 Delete Node from Course

While node deletion focuses on the node itself, it is also necessary to address scenarios where a node's connection to a specific course should be severed without deleting the node. This is achieved through the server-side route `/delete/course-from-node`. This action is performed at the `server/update` server end point as it requires inserting data and updating the server.

```
const deleteQuery = `
PREFIX ex: <http://localhost:8080/>

DELETE WHERE {
  ex:${nodeId} ex:in_course ?courseBlankNode .
  ?courseBlankNode ex:course ex:${courseCode} .
  ?courseBlankNode ex:bloom_taxonomy_level ?bt1 .
}
`;

If unlinking is successful:
  Send success response
Else:
  Send failure response
```

```
Function unlinkNodeFromCourse(nodeID):
  response <- send POST request to '/node/remove/course' with nodeID and
  course

  If response indicates success:
    Log success message
    Return true
  Else:
    Handle root node or other unlinking errors
    Return false
```

Upon triggering this route, the node's ID and the course code are extracted from the incoming request. A SPARQL deletion query is crafted, aiming to unlink the node

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from the particular course, ensuring that no residues of the association remain. Once the query is executed and the link is successfully broken, a confirmation is sent back to the client side. Client-side management of this operation is handled by the function `unlinkNodeFromCourse`. It prepares the request with the relevant node and course details and forwards it to the server. Post-request, the response is parsed. Successful operations result in a log confirmation. Otherwise, appropriate errors, including attempts to unlink root nodes, are handled and presented to the user.

4.5 Assessing Course Objective

A course consists of multiple subdomains. Each subdomain has multiple topics, represented by a count. Each topic falls under a specific taxonomy level. The assessment of course objectives is based on the distribution of these topics across subdomains and their alignment with Bloom's taxonomy levels.

We employ a two-level donut chart developed using the D3.js Framework to visualize this distribution. The inner circle represents the different subdomains, while the outer circle shows Bloom's taxonomy levels. A course consists of multiple subdomains. Each subdomain has multiple topics, represented by a count. Each topic falls under a specific taxonomy level. Since all the topics have a Bloom's taxonomy level associated with each course, we compute course objectives by analyzing the distribution of the topic's subdomains and Bloom's taxonomy level. The resulting statistics are an accurate overview of the course, and thus, if the course objectives align with Bloom's taxonomy, it ensures that the course is designed to promote a comprehensive and systematic approach to learning. Moreover, the instructors can use this statistic to assess the effectiveness of their topic and subdomain coverage and make necessary adjustments. Furthermore, aligning course objectives with Bloom's taxonomy can help evaluate learners' progress and performance throughout the course.

The course statistics are presented in tabular data and a donut chart using the D3.js Framework. The donut chart has two concentric circles representing two data levels, namely subdomain (inner) and taxonomy level (outer). The colors and arcs help differentiate between data points, while the legends are generated for the inner circle, showing the different subdomains. The chart also displays labels that show the percentages for each section. Subdomains are sorted based on their percentage of the total, and within each subdomain, taxonomy levels are sorted by their percentage.

1. Fetch course information:
 - a. Use fetch API to get course data.
 - b. Compute the total topic count.
2. Create inner circle data:
 - a. For each subdomain, compute start and end angles.³
3. Create outer circle data:
 - a. For each subdomain's taxonomy, determine start and end angles.
4. Draw the inner circle.
5. Add percentage labels to the inner circle.
6. Draw the outer circle.
7. Add leader lines for outer circle labels.
8. Draw outer circle labels with percentages.
9. Add legends for the inner circle subdomains.
10. Sort subdomains by their percentages.
11. Populate the table with sorted subdomain data and taxonomy levels.

```

SPARQL Query for fetching information
const courseDetailsQuery = `
PREFIX ex: <http://localhost:8080/>
SELECT
  ?subDomain
  ?totalTopicsInSubDomain
  ?taxonomyLevel
  ?taxonomyTopicCount
  ((?taxonomyTopicCount * 1.0 / ?totalTopicsInSubDomain) AS ?percentage)
WHERE {
  {
    # This subquery calculates the total number of topics in each
    subdomain
    SELECT ?subDomain (COUNT(DISTINCT ?topic) AS
      ?totalTopicsInSubDomain)
    WHERE {
      ?topic a ex:Topic ;
        ex:in_course/ex:course ex:Course${course} ;
        ex:sub_domain ?subDomain .
    }
  }
  GROUP BY ?subDomain

```

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```
    }
    {
      # This subquery counts the number of topics per taxonomy level
      SELECT ?subDomain ?taxonomyLevel (COUNT(DISTINCT ?topic)
                                             AS ?taxonomyTopicCount)

      WHERE {
        ?topic a ex:Topic ;
              ex:in_course/ex:course ex:Course${course} ;
              ex:in_course/ex:bloom_taxonomy_level ?taxonomyLevel ;
              ex:sub_domain ?subDomain .
      }
      GROUP BY ?subDomain ?taxonomyLevel
    }
  }
ORDER BY ?subDomain ?taxonomyLevel
';
```

Using the `fetch` API, we retrieve course data and compute the total topic count. We then leverage `D3.js` to create the two concentric circles, with the inner circle representing subdomains and the outer circle denoting taxonomy levels. Each segment in the inner circle is colored uniquely using the `d3.scaleOrdinal` function. The outer circle's segments are color-interpolated based on the parent subdomain. For enhancing comprehension, percentage labels and legends are added.

Instructors can then refer to this visualization and the tabulated data to evaluate the topic distribution and their alignment with Bloom's taxonomy. If there is a skew or misalignment, necessary adjustments can be made to ensure holistic and adequate coverage.

5

Results

The result is a web portal that displays the contents of the RDF store through HTTP requests. It has the functionality to display the TCG of a course, CRUD functionalities for it and provide a detailed overview of the course and its objective.

5.1 Construction of TCG

The Topic Curriculum Graph (TCG) for the course "Distributed and Parallel Programming - 5062COPP6Y" and "Web Data Processing Systems - XM_40020" was constructed to represent the interconnected topics within the course. As depicted in Figure 5.3, the TCG showcases only the topics specific to this course. Figure 5.1 shows an interface that enables users to seamlessly input course data, laying the foundational structure for the subsequent generation of a TCG. Figure 5.2 presents the main web interface that allows users to view the TCG of a selected course. Delving deeper into the course specifics, Figure 5.3 showcases the detailed TCG for the course "Distributed and Parallel Programming - 5062COPP6Y". To enhance the flexibility of the TCG, several functionalities were introduced. Users can create and incorporate a new node into the course, as Figure 5.4 illustrates. Moreover, nodes can be removed from the course as depicted in Figure 5.5, and their associated information can be updated as demonstrated in Figure 5.6. For connectivity purposes, the system provides a form, seen in Figure 5.7, which permits the linkage of any two unconnected nodes. The feature is also to connect nodes from a selected range as portrayed in Figure 5.8. Conversely, if there is a need to remove existing connections, users can utilize the form presented in Figure 5.9 or opt to disconnect nodes from a selection, shown in Figure 5.10.

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Upload CSV

Course Name:

Course Code:

CSV File:
 No file chosen

Figure 5.1: Web interface to Add Course data to create TCG

Figure 5.2: Web Interface to view TCG of a particular course

5.1 Construction of TCG

Figure 5.6: Form to update node information

Figure 5.7: Form to connect any two unconnected nodes

Figure 5.8: Connect nodes from selection

Figure 5.9: Form to disconnect any two connected nodes

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Figure 5.10: Disconnect nodes from selection

5.2 Assessing Course Objective

The Course Objective section offers a statistical overview of the distribution of topics across subdomains. Additionally, it provides insights into the Bloom's taxonomy level for each topic within these subdomains. Figure 5.11 presents this distribution in tabular form, while Figure 5.12 visualizes the statistics in a donut chart. While this assessment gives a detailed overview of the course content, its accuracy and usefulness are contingent on the TCG's quality.

5.2 Assessing Course Objective

Course Objective

Course5062COPP6Y		CourseXM_40020			
Subdomain	Topic Count	Percentage of Total	Taxonomy Level	Taxonomy Count	Percentage in Subdomain
SubDomainComputerArchitecture	104	68.87%	BTL_Understand	76	73.08%
			BTL_Remember	17	16.35%
			BTL_Apply	6	5.77%
			BTL_Analyse	5	4.81%
SubDomainDecentralisedApplications	27	17.88%	BTL_Understand	13	48.15%
			BTL_Remember	9	33.33%
			BTL_Apply	3	11.11%
			BTL_Analyse	2	7.41%
SubDomainParallelComputing	9	5.96%	BTL_Understand	4	44.44%
			BTL_Analyse	2	22.22%
			BTL_Remember	2	22.22%
			BTL_Apply	1	11.11%
SubDomainWebApplications	8	5.30%	BTL_Understand	4	50.00%
			BTL_Remember	3	37.50%
			BTL_Analyse	1	12.50%
SubDomainComputerNetworks	3	1.99%	BTL_Understand	3	100.00%

Figure 5.11: Resulting Course Objective Statistics (tabular)

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Figure 5.12: Resulting Course Objective Statistics (donut)

6

Validation

6.1 Functional Testing

6.1.1 Construction and Visualisation of TCG

6.1.2 Converting input data into TCG

The initial phase of the testing journey began with validating the ETL (Extract, Transform, Load) processes. The intent was to ascertain that topics were correctly stored and that the hierarchical relationships were translated seamlessly. Additional checks included error logging mechanisms and deduplication processes. For detailed test cases and validations, refer to Table 6.1.

Test	Validation
Topics are stored as an RDF	✓
Hierarchy is accurately transferred into ttl	✓
Errors and Warnings are registered	✓
Identical topics are merged	✓

Table 6.1: Functional Testing of ETL process of Input Data

6.1.2.1 Nodes and Links

With the data integrated into the TCG, the focus shifted to its visualization. Both nodes and links, the fundamental building blocks of TCG, underwent rigorous tests. The nodes' visual representation, interactive features, and the links' integrity and behavior in various scenarios were scrutinized. For specific validations, refer to Tables 6.2 and 6.3.

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Test	Validation
Nodes & labels are displayed accurately on initial load	✓
Nodes have a red glow on selection	✓
Nodes can be smoothly dragged	✓

Table 6.2: Functional Testing of Visualized Nodes

Test	Validation
Links are connected accurately on initial load	✓

Table 6.3: Functional Testing of Visualized Links

6.1.3 TCG Operations

To maintain the dynamic nature of TCG, various CRUD operations (Create, Read, Update, Delete) were examined. This included ensuring uniqueness during creation, accuracy during reading and updating, and irretrievability post deletion. These tests were vital to ensure the stability of the TCG in real-time operations. The specific validations for each operation can be found in Tables 6.4, 6.5, 6.6, and 6.7.

Test	Validation
Unique ID verification (prevention of duplicates)	✓
Created node/link is visible on TCG	✓
Errors and Warnings are registered	✓

Table 6.4: Functional Testing of Creating Nodes and Links in TCG

Test	Validation
Accurate Data Retrieval	✓

Table 6.5: Functional Testing of Reading Nodes and Links in TCG

Test	Validation
Accurate Data Modification	✓
No data duplication	✓
Node and link property retention	✓

Table 6.6: Functional Testing of Updating Nodes in TCG

Test	Validation
Node is removed from course	✓
Link is removed from TCG	✓
Removed node/link cannot be retrieved	✓

Table 6.7: Functional Testing of Deleting Nodes and Links in TCG

6.1.4 Course Objective Generation

A separate evaluation set was dedicated to the system’s capacity to generate course objectives. These tests assessed the TCG’s proficiency in topic distribution analysis and generating accurate course statistics. Detailed outcomes are in Table 6.8.

Test	Validation
Topic distribution analysis	✓
Accurate course statistics	✓

Table 6.8: Functional Testing of Course Objective

6.2 Interaction Testing

6.2.1 Visualization of TCG

6.2.1.1 Nodes

Nodes form the foundational building blocks of the TCG. Ensuring seamless interaction with these nodes is vital. Table 6.9 overviews the interaction tests on visualized nodes. These tests confirm the mechanisms for selecting nodes and the visibility parameters for neighboring nodes.

Test	Validation
Nodes can only be selected while holding Ctrl/Cmd key	✓
Only Neighboring Nodes are visible when hovered on Nodes	✓

Table 6.9: Interaction Testing of Visualized Nodes

6.2.1.2 Links

Links visually represent the relationships between nodes. Their dynamic nature, especially when repositioning or interacting with nodes, requires thorough testing. Table 6.10 show-

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cases the interaction tests centered around these visualized links, validating their persistent connections and visibility criteria.

Test	Validation
Links are connected even after repositioning nodes	✓
Only Neighboring Links of nodes are visible when hovered on Nodes	✓

Table 6.10: Interaction Testing of Visualized Links

6.2.2 TCG Operations

We address the critical functionalities tied to the manipulation and management of nodes within the Topic Curriculum Graph (TCG). The table labeled 6.11 delineates the primary operations—creation, reading, and deletion of nodes. The tests ensure the intuitive pop-up forms for node creation, the prevention of duplicate IDs to maintain data integrity, the precise extraction and display of node information upon selection, and the confirmation safeguards during the node deletion process. Through these interaction tests, the goal is to guarantee the reliability and efficiency of node operations within the TCG.

Test	Validation
[Create]Pop-up form upon click	✓ Create>Create
Restricts duplicate IDs	✓ Read>Read
Extract relevant node information on the selection	✓ Read>Read
Update drop-downs with accurate node information	✓ Delete>Delete
Confirm node deletion process	✓

Table 6.11: Interaction Testing of TCG Operation

6.2.3 Course Objective Analysis

Interaction testing ensures that the system’s user interface and interactivity features operate seamlessly. This involves confirming that buttons, forms, and other interactive components respond correctly to user inputs. The following table 6.12 will delineate the results of our interaction testing, providing insights into the system’s usability and responsiveness.

Test	Validation
Button click events	✓
Displaying course details in modal	✓
The interactivity of pie chart (hover, click)	✓

Table 6.12: Interaction Testing of Course Objective

6.3 Visual Testing

6.3.1 Construction of TCG

6.3.1.1 Nodes

Within Visual Testing, the Topic Curriculum Graph (TCG) requires meticulous attention to its aesthetics and functionality, ensuring clarity and user-friendliness. As delineated in table 6.13, nodes undergo rigorous visual tests as fundamental units of the TCG. The size and color of each node are designed to directly correspond to its significance in the course, offering users an immediate visual cue regarding the importance of different concepts. This not only enhances understandability but also improves the overall user experience.

Test	Validation
Node size varies based on its importance in the course	✓
Node color varies based on its importance in the course	✓

Table 6.13: Visual Testing of Visualized Nodes

6.3.1.2 Links

Beyond nodes, links play a crucial role in denoting the interconnection of concepts. As presented in the subsequent table (note: there seems to be a redundancy in label names, as both tables are labeled 6.14), ensuring the persistence of links after node repositioning is essential for maintaining the integrity of the TCG. Furthermore, enhancing the user experience, only the neighboring links are visible when hovered upon, preventing overwhelming visual clutter and facilitating focused interaction.

Test	Validation
Links are active even after nodes are dragged	✓
Only neighboring links are visible when hovered	✓

Table 6.14: Visual Testing of Visualized Links

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6.3.2 TCG Operations

The visualization aspect of the Topic Curriculum Graph (TCG) is pivotal in ensuring a clear representation of the data and its associations. The table represented by 6.15 delves into nodes' visibility and structural integrity during their lifecycle stages - creation, reading, updating, and deletion. It ensures that newly created nodes are visible and harmonized with the existing TCG structure. Moreover, the nodes should present accurate details upon selection and offer flexibility for linking, unlinking, and editing, and once deleted, they should no longer remain visible in the TCG. 6.16

Test	Validation
[Create] Node is visible in the TCG	✓ Create>Cr
Node does not disrupt TCG structure	✓ Read>Re
Node details are accurate during selection	✓ Update>Up
Nodes can be linked and unlinked on the TCG [Update] Nodes can be edited on the TCG	✓ Delete>De
Deleted node disappears from TCG	✓

Table 6.15: Visualization Testing of TCG Operations

6.3.3 Course Objective Analysis

The visual presentation of data is often as crucial as the data itself. Effective visualization ensures that users can easily comprehend and interpret the information. Our system's visualization components, including charts, graphs, and tables, underwent rigorous testing to guarantee clarity, accuracy, and effectiveness. The results of this evaluation are summarized in the ensuing table 6.16

Test	Validation
Correct color assignment for inner pie chart	✓
Correct color assignment for outer pie chart	✓
Correct labeling of legends	✓
Proper rendering of leader lines	✓
Accurate percentages displayed	✓
Responsive chart adjustments	✓

Table 6.16: Visualization Testing of Course Objective

7

Discussion

Introducing Topic Curriculum Graphs (TCGs) heralds a new age in academic navigation. Their aim to encapsulate and map the intricate connections between courses and their encompassed concepts can revolutionize how educators, students, and academic institutions approach curriculum planning and course selection. Through this research's analytical approach, it becomes clear that TCGs have the potential to provide a detailed, transparent, and holistic representation of academic content. However, the TCG does not merge with the existing ontology available on the internet and thus will have to be restructured to merge into the data available on the internet.

The primary focus areas include the Schema selection for TCG, its construction from current curricula, essential tools and techniques, the representation of a course with TCG.

TCGs offer educators a comprehensive overview of course content distribution, pinpointing areas needing more in-depth exploration. For students, TCGs serve as a valuable tool, providing clarity on course content and aiding informed decision-making for course selection. Academic institutions can leverage TCGs for optimized resource allocation, ensuring that courses are designed and offered in alignment with demand and academic importance.

Based on our experiment, we aim to answer our SRQs and then the RQ highlighting our solution and applications.

7.1 SRQ1: Which Schema is preferred for a TCG?

The preferred schema for a Topic Curriculum Graph (TCG) would depend on the specific goals, requirements, and design choices of the educational platform or organization implementing the TCG. Schemas serves distinct purposes in representing various educational concepts and their relationships within the curriculum.

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For our purpose of construct a semantically solid TCG, we opted for a schema centered around the Topic Schema integrated with Subject Schema, Prerequisite Schema and Competency Schema. This selection allowed us to create an RDF structure seen in Figures 3.4 and 3.4.

The design allows us to reuse existing Keys with multiple courses and thus improves significant data management. Furthermore, the interoperability of this design allows for scalable improvement of the TCG.

7.2 SRQ2: Construction of a Topic Curriculum Graph (TCG) from Current Curricula

To construct a TCG, the process can be broken down into systematic steps. The creation of a TCG as proposed in this study stems from the increasing need for structured, visual, and analytical approaches to curriculum design and understanding. By translating textual and often fragmented curriculum data into a cohesive and interrelated graph, educators, learners, and stakeholders can perceive the nuances of the educational journey. Furthermore, such a graph assists in identifying potential gaps, redundancies, or misalignment's in the curriculum, empowering course designers with data-driven insights.

To ensure the construction of a comprehensive and representative Topic Curriculum Graph (TCG), the process starts with the extraction of raw data. This involves a thorough examination of the current curricula, with the fetch API playing a vital role in gathering indexed topics that serve as the foundational nodes for the graph.

Once topics are extracted, they are classified based on a two-pronged hierarchy. The first step involves breaking down topics into broader subdomains, and subsequently into detailed taxonomy levels. This hierarchical classification provides the structural backbone of the TCG, creating a tiered and interconnected representation of curricular content.

The relationship between topics, subdomains, and taxonomy levels is depicted using a graph-based approach. The TCG is multi-dimensional, representing both the breadth and depth of the curriculum. Each topic (or node) is connected to others based on its relevance and category. Moreover, the taxonomy levels add another dimension to this graph, integrating the depth of understanding required for each topic.

To make the TCG more accessible and comprehensible, D3.js is utilized for graphical representation. This tool offers dynamic, interactive visualizations, allowing for real-time exploration and understanding of the curriculum's structure.

7.3 SRQ3: Essential Tools and Techniques for TCG Construction

Constructing a Topic Curriculum Graph (TCG) involves a delicate symphony of data acquisition, structuring, visualization, and storage mechanisms. The fetch API initially anchors the data-gathering phase, a tool known for its prowess and inefficient data extraction. With its asynchronous operations, this API facilitates the seamless retrieval of vast curriculum datasets, setting the stage for a comprehensive TCG. Once the raw data is extracted, organizing and classifying this information in a meaningful hierarchy is vital. Topics are systematically sorted into broader subdomains, further subdivided into more nuanced taxonomy levels. Within this context, Bloom's taxonomy emerges as a fundamental pillar, providing the TCG with its pedagogical backbone. By juxtaposing curriculum topics with specific cognitive skills detailed in Bloom's framework, the TCG transforms into an insightful educational map, harmonizing course content with learning objectives. However, the architecture and classification of the TCG are only as valuable as its storage and retrieval mechanisms. Apache Jena, a revered RDF store, offers an ideal solution. As the TCG's database, Jena stores data in the RDF format, ensuring semantic richness and data interoperability. With RDF's unique subject-predicate-object triple format, intricate relationships between curriculum topics are crystallized, allowing for an in-depth exploration of the curriculum landscape. Furthermore, the inherent querying capability of Jena, powered by SPARQL, provides educators with a dynamic tool to extract tailored insights, making the TCG adaptable to various educational scenarios. However, to truly harness the TCG's potential, its structure and insights need to be visualized in an accessible manner. D3.js, a premier visualization tool, translates the TCG's complex data into an interactive visual canvas.

7.4 SRQ4: How can a TCG be utilized to represent a course?

Let's break down a course. A course consists of lectures which addresses topics at different understanding levels. This TCG which dominantly has a topic schema allows for topics to hold course metadata as seen in Figure 3.4. We select all topics in the course to construct a TCG of that course. The hierarchy can be expressed through the count of children and grandchildren nodes for each topic along with its taxonomy level. This results in a Course TCG as shown in Figure 5.3. A course can be managed by managing the topics and realigning the topics and objectives with the course objectives.

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Since each topic has its own taxonomy for the course, we compute course objective based on the count of topics in each subdomain and count of each taxonomy level per subdomain. This results in a statistically significant course objective derived solely from the contents of the course. Utilising these methods, we can accurately represent courses in TCG.

7.5 RQ: How do Topic Curriculum Graphs aid in understanding and representation of course content?

Topic Curriculum Graphs offer a comprehensive and structured method for understanding academic curricula. Through our research, we have explored various tools and techniques to develop TCGs that accurately represent the internal structure of a curriculum. These TCGs serve as visual analysis platforms, aiding educators and students in navigating and comprehending the curriculum landscape more effectively. Our study highlights how TCGs influence the representation and understanding of course content.

7.5.1 Understanding Course Content

The inherent structure of a Topic Curriculum Graph offers a comprehensive and integrated visualization of course content. Its multiple layers, ranging from topics to sub-domains and their interconnected relationships, empower educators, students, and institutions with a transparent representation of curricular complexities.

- **Comprehensive Representation:** As established through SRQ2 and SRQ4, the construction and utilization of a TCG provide a meticulous breakdown of courses. They elucidate course objectives, major themes, underlying topics, and their hierarchical arrangements, effectively capturing the essence of academic content.
- **Semantic Robustness:** The unique schema preference, as highlighted in SRQ1, endows the TCG with a semantically-rich backbone. This ensures that academic themes are not only represented but also contextualized, thereby facilitating a deeper understanding.
- **Interconnectedness:** TCGs thrive on highlighting the links between various academic concepts. This aids in visualizing prerequisites, dependencies, and the flow of information within courses.

Conclusion

Topic Curriculum Graphs (TCGs) are the precipice of redefining academic navigation and resource management. Their potential to merge the technological with the academic paves the way for an interconnected and efficient academic landscape. While challenges in construction and maintenance are inherent, their far-reaching implications cannot be denied. The study focused on developing a Topic Curriculum Graph for each course based on user input of hierarchical topics. The researchers encountered challenges regarding the TCG's semantics, which depended solely from the input data. The structural design is scalable and data is re-usable due to RDF triples. Additionally, the study examined the Course Objective using statistical analysis to examine how topics are distributed across subdomains (Figure 5.11 and Figure 5.12). This analysis provided insights into Bloom's taxonomy level for topics within a subdomain. However, it was observed that the effectiveness and accuracy of this analysis heavily depend on the quality of the TCG. Overall, this research pointed out challenges related to developing a semantically stable TCG and emphasized the impact of an unreliable or inaccurate TCG on statistical analysis of course objectives. The findings underscored the importance of continuously enhancing the quality of the TCG to ensure its reliability, accuracy, scalability, and maintainability. TCGs demand continuous updates to ensure they remain relevant and practical. Once a robust, semantically-solid network of topics is established, adding new topics becomes relatively straightforward, with courses quickly tapping into the existing structure. With the potential integration of student scores, the TCGs can be further enhanced, leading to even more personalized learning for students. Given their comprehensive nature and the heuristic overview they provide of course content, it is plausible to envision TCGs as a staple in academic institutions, not just as a supplementary tool but as a primary reference point for curriculum design, course selection, and academic navigation.

9

Future Work

As academia continually evolves and grows, so does the potential for enhancing and expanding TCGs:

9.1 Semantical Solidity Refinement

Continuous iterations and refinements are paramount to ensure the semantic accuracy of the TCGs. Introducing algorithms or methodologies that can dynamically adjust based on new lecture content or external academic developments will be crucial.

9.2 Automated topic and heirarchy extraction

This research was analyzed over a hierarchical list of topics of a course but the input data must be automatically generated by analyzing lecture slides, course catalog and assignments in the course. This will lead to an accurate representation of the course and thus will reduce time for construction of input data.

9.3 Integration of Feedback Loops

Factoring in student feedback on topics can help in authentic categorization and even in adjusting Bloom's taxonomy categorization of each topic, ensuring the TCGs are robust and relevant.

9.4 Diversifying Data Sources

While this research focused on heirarchical topics, there is potential to integrate assignments and valuable student feedback into TCGs. This would provide a more rounded view of the academic landscape, taking into account both curriculum design and student perceptions.

9.5 Scaling and Refinement

As TCGs expand to cover more subjects and academic levels, there is a need to ensure they remain accurate and relevant. Incorporating best practices from current leading curriculum management systems and adapting them to the TCG framework will be pivotal.

9.6 Interdisciplinary Analysis

There lies an untapped potential in interlinking courses from various disciplines, offering students insights into interdisciplinary studies and opportunities.

Figure 9.1: RDF Structure of Student Scores

9.7 Interoperability with existing Ontologies

The current ontological design of the TCG does not match nor merge with the existing academic knowledge graph ontologies. Further research into restructuring the TCG to merge with administrative academic ontologies are to be conducted. The TCG is not a Knowledge Graph but uses several techniques of knowledge graph and has to be enchanced in future research.

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